

TRADITION AND INNOVATION IN THE HISTORICAL POEMS OF THE INDEPENDENCE PERIOD

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Abstract In this article, which analyzes the poems of the period of independence, scientific conclusions are given about what is originality and innovation in traditional and modern poems, as well as the reflection of historical figures or times.

Key words Tradition in the poem, innovation, historical epics, time, depiction of historical figures, talmeh, fine arts.

Tradition is the proper development of the best intellectual and artistic resources left from the literature of the past by the literature of the next period. The best achievements of the literature of the past or the literature of other nations can be a literary tradition. For example, Navoi promoted the ideas of humanity, heroism, friendship of peoples, hatred of tyranny and injustice in his works. These ideas were developed by later writers, or Abdulla Qadiri took the form of a novel by Walter Scott and George Zaydon and created a completely new Uzbek national novel on this basis. It is clear to all of us that Erkin Vahidov developed the ghazal genre in classical literature with a new spirit and meaning. To analyze, the tradition is as follows:

- Ideological tradition. This is the development of humanitarian, heroic ideas and motives, as in Navoi.

- The tradition of types. It is the adoption and development of the traditions of image creation by the artists of the next generation. Farhod-Azizkhan-Euklion, Gobsek-Kori Ishkamba are examples of the tradition of these types.

- Formal traditions. It is important to note that the worldview of ideological traditions is developed by writers close to each other. Formal traditions can also be developed by writers with different worldviews. Because the artistic form is neutral to the worldview. But each writer can subjugate the existing form based on his worldview. So, shakily tradition is the genres, images, weight and rhymes inherited from the previous ones and developed by later writers. Traditions in the field of artistic form can be continued as follows:

Development of existing genre forms;

Synthesizing the traditions of the past;

Creating a completely new genre, partially using an existing form; For example: poem, novel, ghazal, lyrical story. "Reviving" old forms. Today, the artistic updates, formal and content researches in Uzbek literature are related to the changes in national thinking due to the achievement of independence. In fact, during the years of independence, the philosophical and intellectual tone of Uzbek poetry became stronger. In prose, reflecting the human psyche, a wide range of passions and emotions in various conflicting colors, portraying the problems occupying the consciousness of mankind with all their complexity, striving to reveal the high national, universal essence of the individual in a special way has become a leading direction. As an expression of the changes in the social consciousness, it began to determine the nature and scope of methodological and formal researches, to penetrate into the deep layers of the mental world, to discover new forms and principles of perception of the changing spiritual world. Creativity, belief and attitude to the word have been radically renewed.

When it comes to traditional epics, in the poetry of our classic literature, there are works consisting of whole letters, sometimes including letters. For example, "Alpomish" or A. Navoi's epics "Munshaot", "Farhad and Shirin", "Layli and Majnun" are important in this regard. In modern poetry, we can say that K. Rahimbayeva's "End of Winter" and Sh. Qurban's epics "Onam koshidasan or a letter to my sister" are examples of works in this direction. Another traditional

style of epic writing is written in the form of a poem. Such epics are characterized by a wide range of opportunities to describe life reality in a coherent and detailed manner. Because large-scale epics written in masnavi performed the artistic and aesthetic functions of novels and short stories in prose, they were significant for their scale, plot, composition, epic characters, and fluent reading. A. Navoi's "Lison ut-Tayr", "Khamsa", M. Salih's "Shaybaniynoma" written in this form are examples of classic literature, and in our modern literature "Tashkentnoma" by M. Shaykhzoda, "Sunspring" by J. Kamal, M. Epics such as Ali's "Beshgul" and E. Samandar's "Erk Sadolari" are new creative works that continue the masnavi style. In addition, there are a number of epics that reflect the continuation of the traditions of folk folklore in the epics. There are a number of epics that reflect aspects such as the use of the art of sajj, the introduction of the tone and motif of folk epics, the proportion of prose and verse, and the use of finger weights in today's poems. In particular, in the poem "Ishq" by A. Mahkam, the persons who renounced this mortal life in the path of divine love and suffered in the path of righteous love are described through the symbol of Gado qalandar. Another epic of the artist "Tavajjuh" continues the tradition of creating Babur's personality. The superiority of the lyric-epic expression is noticeable in the poem together with the mystical content. It highlights the important aspects of Babur's character in the fate of the country and the country. Babur's worldview, inner experiences, heartaches were expressed through letters. Another epic of the poet "Fatiha" begins with praise to Allah in accordance with the traditional form. According to S.N.Ibrahim, modern features in A.Mahkam's poems are significant as they depict the psyche and suffering of people living in the vortex of eternal and eternal tragedies. The poems "Alisher" by T. Nizam and "Naqshband" by E. Shukur are just such works. These epics also belong to the series of historical philosophical poems.

After they smelled the soil of the Hindus

Abay was the height of the wind.

"From this soil comes a heat of the earth,

It is Qasri Hinduvan with land interest

The day will come, Qasri Orifon will be"

In the work, the author describes the most important aspects of Naqshband's life in a historical and philosophical form. The prophecy about the birth of the hero, especially in A. Navoi's work "Nasayim ul-Muhabbat", is a valid historical source. So, the arrival of a great, perfect person in the world is predicted by the elders, and he will bring good news to people. Among modern poems, the traditional feature of O. Matjon's "Ming bir yogdu" reminds of the style of A. Navoi's "Mahbub ul-Qulub" epic. That is, moral and philosophical thoughts are expressed in prose form, and then the concluding views are given in verse form. Rubaiy, khita, fards, which are written in accordance with the mentioned reasoning, express the content and philosophy of the epic in a deeper way. In his works, A.Navoi provides a wide range of observational opinions, provides evidence, and makes reasonable conclusions. For example, he explains his thoughts about satisfaction, definition of words, language, and justice with reasonable narrations and poetic passages.

Everyone has the great quality of contentment.

There will be honor and respect in all countries,

Anyone who builds on greed and greed,

It looks good and bad.

It seems that it can be said that expressing the peculiarities of the poems of our classical literature in modern epics, continuing the traditional style, and searching for a new form and content in the poems of the independence period paid off in a certain sense.

Analyzing modern poems, it is worth taking a look at J. Kamal's "Armon", "Varakhsha", G. Jorayeva's "Zuhro Star", E. Samandar's "Sounds of Man". The signs of traditionalism are embodied in them, and the poem "Varakhsha" leads the reader to the events of the 7th century. This epic covers the historical events related to the arrival of the Arabs in Movarounnahr. In it, historical figures, scenes of the

historical period are depicted in an artistically wonderful form. It should be said that the use of the masnavi style makes the heavy historical background of the epic a little smoother and easier to read.

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